

o-(Imine-N-acetylaceton) Benzene Sulphonic Acid as a Gravimetric Reagent for Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II)

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o-(Imine-N-acetylaceton) benzene sulphonic acid (H_2AB) has been used as a gravimetric reagent for Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II). The solid metal chelates formed possess 1:1 metal-ligand stoichiometry. On the basis of magnetic and I.R. studies octahedral structures are suggested for these chelates.

RECENTLY Holm et al.¹ have reviewed the metal chelates of the Schiff bases. Several metal chelates of the Schiff bases are solid and have, therefore, found applications in gravimetry. A perusal of the literature¹ indicates that no systematic study has been made on the Schiff base, *o*-(imine-N-acetylaceton) benzene sulphonic acid (H_2AB) derived from acetylaceton and *o*-aminobenzenesulphonic acid. It is a biprotic tridentate ligand containing a sulphonic group, an enolic hydroxyl group and a donor nitrogen atom, and it forms solid metal chelates² with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and $UO_2(II)$.

The cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) chelates are insoluble in water and can thus form the basis for their quantitative separation procedures

Experimental

Apparatus : The molecular weights of the chelates in pyridine were determined by semimicro Gallenkamp Ebulliometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on the Gouy magnetic balance using mercury (II) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate as the reference. Their I.R. studies were carried out in Nujol mull on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer provided with sodium chloride prism.

Reagent : H_2AB was prepared by the method of Pfeiffer et al.². Found C, 51.81; H, 4.99; N, 5.47; S, 12.41; ($C_{11}H_{13}NSO_4$) requires C, 51.76; H, 5.09; N, 5.49 and S, 12.54%.

A 5% solution of this reagent was prepared in aqueous-ethanol for use in the gravimetric determinations of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II).

The stock solutions were prepared by dissolving AnalaR (BDH) cobalt(II) nitrate, nickel sulphate and copper(II) sulphate and their metal contents were determined by standard methods⁴.

Gravimetric Determination of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper (II) : An aliquot of the metal-ion solution was placed in a 250 ml pyrex beaker. The pH values

were adjusted with suitable buffers between 5.5 and 6.0 of the Co(II) solution, between 4.5 and 5.5 of the Ni(II) solution and between 3.5 and 4.2 of the Cu(II) solution. To these solutions the reagent was added gradually with constant stirring. Using aqueous-ammonia (2 M) the pH of Co(II) and Ni(II) solutions were raised to 7.7 and 6.5 respectively. Chocolate, dull green and light blue coloured precipitates of the metal chelates were formed in Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) solutions respectively, which were heated at 100°-110° for 10 min, cooled and filtered through sintered glass crucible. The precipitates were washed with aqueous-alcohol until free from the reagent, filtered, and dried at 100° and weighed as $[M(C_{11}H_{11}NSO_4)(H_2O)_3]$ where M= Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II).

The results obtained from the above determinations are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE I—RESULTS OF GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF COBALT(II), NICKEL(II) AND COPPER(II)

	Metal, mgm		Error %
	Found	Taken	
Wt. of Co(II) chelate			
290.11	46.55	46.70	0.29
270.38	43.68	43.54	0.32
220.30	35.33	35.49	0.45
160.65	25.73	25.87	0.53
Wt. of Ni(II) chelate			
280.99	45.00	45.10	0.22
250.75	40.12	40.24	0.29
210.15	33.65	33.73	0.23
150.80	24.15	24.20	0.20
Wt. of Cu(II) chelate			
260.12	44.42	44.60	0.40
230.78	39.49	39.57	0.20
175.15	29.89	30.03	0.46
150.90	25.79	25.87	0.30

Estimation of nickel(II) and copper(II) in presence of each other: The mixture consisting of nickel(II) and copper(II) was adjusted to pH 3.5-4.5 using sodium acetate (2%) solution and 1.5 g of ammonium thiocyanate was added. The solution was heated at 70°-75° and the reagent solution was gradually added with constant stirring, with the dropwise addition of aqueous ammonia (2 M), the pH was raised to 7.5-7.7 when the copper chelate precipitated out. The solution was heated to 100° for 5 min, cooled, filtered and the precipitate was washed, dried, and weighed as described earlier.

The filtrate and washings consisting of nickel(II) was concentrated, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and boiled to decompose the nickel-thiocyanate. After boiling the solution for 10 minutes its pH was raised to 4.5-5.0 with sodium acetate (2%) solution and nickel chelate was precipitated as already described earlier.

Effect of foreign ions in the estimation of nickel (II) and copper(II): In these determinations Fe³⁺ and V⁵⁺ were masked with the help of sodium potassium tartarate and Ti⁴⁺ was masked by using potassium fluoride. Anions like SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻, PO₄³⁻ and F⁻ did not interfere in the pH range 7.5-7.7 but CO₃²⁺ interferes as it also forms a precipitate with the reagent, hence the solution should be free from Co²⁺.

Structure: The cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper (II) chelates were analysed for their elements; their molecular weights as determined ebullioscopically were found to be 359.17, 365.11 and 360.10 and they displayed 5.12, 3.11 and 1.89 B. M. at 98°A as their magnetic moments, suggesting the presence of 3, 2 and 1 electron in their molecules respectively. On the basis of these data the composition [M(C₁₁H₁₁NSO₄)(H₂O)₃] may be assigned to the metal chelates under study.

The structures of the metal chelates have been confirmed by I.R. spectra. An examination of the I.R. spectra of the reagent have shown five bands at 1160

cm⁻¹, 1635 cm⁻¹, 1640 cm⁻¹, 1670 cm⁻¹ and 3590 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to the presence of $\nu_{\text{SO}_3\text{H}}$, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ (enolic), $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ and ν_{OH} respectively. In all the metal chelates studied above the bands at 1160 cm⁻¹ and 3590 cm⁻¹ could not be located which suggest their elimination due to chelation. The spectra of the metal chelates have indicated three intense bands at 1580 cm⁻¹, 1520 cm⁻¹ and 3000 cm⁻¹. The band at 1580 cm⁻¹ may be due to perturbed carbonyl stretch (frequency being shifted from about 1640 cm⁻¹ in the reagent), 1520 cm⁻¹ band may be assigned to the C=C stretching mode (lowered from 1635 cm⁻¹ in the reagent). The band at 3000 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the presence of chelated water molecules in the chelates. Based on the above studies structure as shown in Fig. 1 may be assigned to the metal chelates.

Fig. 1. Co(II), Ni(II) & Cu(II) Chelates of *o*-(Imine-N-Acetylacetonate) Benzene Sulphonic Acid where M = Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II) and L = H₂O.

References

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